

EFFECTS OF SiCp ON LOW CYCLE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF SiCp/AL COMPOSITE AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURE

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ABSTRACT

The cyclic stress response characteristics and low cyclic fatigue endurance of SiCp/AL composite and its unreinforced aluminum were studied at 441K. The specimens were cycled using tensile-compression loading under plastic strain control. The reinforced and unreinforced aluminum showed continuous cyclic softening behavior except the composite displayed slight cyclic hardening in first loading cycle. The low cycle fatigue resistance of the composite was lower than that of the unreinforced aluminum under higher cyclic strain ranges, but the fatigue resistance of the composite got stronger under lower cyclic strain amplitudes.

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuously reinforced aluminum-based metal-matrix composites exhibit attractive advantages, such as high specific modules, high specific strength, good high cycle fatigue response, low density and facile fabrication. They have emerged as a new class of structural materials for ambient and elevated temperature applications in aerospace and automobile industries. Therefore the mechanical properties of them have been paid a lot of attention[1-5]. However, a limited number of investigations on low cycle fatigue behavior have been reported[6,7], and especially little work has been done in this aspect at elevated temperature[8]. The present study is to investigate cyclic deformation behavior and low cycle fatigue lives among the SiCp/Al composite and its unreinforced counterpart at elevated temperature. Since the cyclic deformation behavior is highly sensitive to matrix microstructure, pure aluminum was selected as matrix material for ensuring the similarity of microstructure between the reinforced matrix and unreinforced material.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

A SiCp/Al composite with 20vol% SiCp and its unreinforced pure aluminum were made by powder metallurgy method. The SiC particles with average size 32 μ m were mechanically mixed with the 14 μ m aluminum powder. The mixture was then hot compacted and subsequently

extruded at 20:1 into 16 mm diameter cylindrical bar stock. The unreinforced matrix aluminum was produced in the same process except for mixing. The chemical composition of the matrix aluminum is given in Ref.[8]. The microstructure of the metal matrix composites is shown in Fig.1. The SiC particles dispersed with a little cluster and were partially aligned along the extrusion direction.

Figure 1. Optical micrographs of SiCp/Al composite (a) transverse plane, (b) longitudinal plane

The test specimens were machined from the as-extruded bars with the loading axis parallel to the extrusion direction. The gauge length and diameter of the specimens were 14mm and 6 mm respectively and conformed to ASTM E606. The surfaces of the specimens were mechanically polished to remove scratches and machine marks.

Tensile tests were conducted in accordance with ASTM E8 using an extensometer of 14 mm gauge length and a crosshead speed of 0.4 mm/min that resulted in an initial strain rate of 4.8×10^{-3} /s. Tensile and fatigue tests were performed on a mechanical servo-controlled testing system at 298 and 441K in air. The specimens were heated in a resistance furnace with a temperature accuracy of ± 3 K. The low cycle fatigue tests were performed under a fully reversed plastic strain control ranging from 1×10^{-3} to 7×10^{-3} . A triangular wave form was used and the mean strain was zero. The cycling frequency was 0.03 Hz for the first 10 cycles and was changed to 0.125 Hz for the rest of fatigue life. An axial clip-on extensometer was used to measure the total strain. The plastic strain control of the test was achieved by keeping the width of the hysteresis loop constant manually. Fatigue life was defined as the number of cycles to cause a rapid drop of the cyclic stress. The fracture surfaces of specimens were examined in a scanning electron microscope to determine the predominant fracture modes and to characterize the fine scale topography of the fatigue fracture surfaces.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TENSILE PROPERTIES

Tensile strength of the composite was generally greater than that of the matrix material. Table 1. lists the elevated temperature tensile properties of the composite and unreinforced material. Incorporation of the reinforcing particles promoted the elastic modulus 36-68% and the tensile proof strength 53%.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the unreinforced matrix and the composite at 441K

SiC content (vol%)	Elastic modulus(GPa)	0.2% proof strength(MPa)	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation (%)	Reduction in area (%)
20	89.6	69.4	84.9	24.0	26.1
0	53.1	45.1	---	---	---

CYCLIC STRESS RESPONSE

The cyclic stress response curves of the unreinforced aluminum and the composite under different plastic strain amplitudes at 441K are shown in Fig. 2. The composite showed few cyclic hardening only in first loading cycle and then softened gradually until failure for all plastic strain amplitudes. The amount of cyclic softening was effected by the plastic strain amplitude. Higher plastic strain amplitudes made the specimens show more cyclic softening. On the other hand, the unreinforced aluminum softened continuously over the whole fatigue life. However, stable region was still seen in same unreinforced aluminum specimens. It was very interesting to note that an increase in frequency from 0.03 Hz to 0.125 Hz led to a higher cyclic stress, as indicated by arrows.

Figure 2. Cyclic stress response curves for the unreinforced aluminum and composite at 441K
(a) aluminum, (b) SiCp/Al composite

As the experimental results indicated above, the characters of the cyclic stress-strain response of pure aluminum and its composite are similar at elevated temperature. It is anticipated that the dislocation structures developed during processing may be responsible for the observed phenomena. The extruded pure aluminum is actually in an annealed condition with lower density of dislocation. If at room temperature, the increase in dislocation density and dislocation interaction during cyclic deformation made the material show initial hardening, cyclic stability and second hardening[9]. However, at elevated temperature the dislocations become more flexible, so they are hard to tangle. Therefore the unreinforced aluminum is only observed to be continuously cyclic softening without initial hardening and second hardening.

There is another situation with the composites, The virgin specimen of the composite is more likely in a work-hardened status with high density of dislocation and thermal residual stress produced during processing due to the large different thermal expansion coefficient between the reinforcement and matrix[10,11]. The existing dislocation configurations are not stable and can be changed under cyclic straining[12] especially at elevated temperature. It is reasonably assumed that the continuous softening is attributed to the rearrangement of the dislocation structure.

PLASTIC STRAIN-LIFE BEHAVIOR

Cyclic plastic strain is a measurable physical quantity that can be related to fatigue damage. Fig 3 compares plastic strain-fatigue life behavior for the composite and unreinforced aluminum at elevated temperature. The unreinforced aluminum has longer fatigue life at high strain regions, but the fatigue resistance of the composite is greater at low strain amplitudes. It may be due to the fatigue lives are so short at high strain amplitudes that some time-dependent factors have not take into action. It is another situation at low strain amplitudes. With enough long time at 0.46Tm(Tm is melting temperature of aluminum), some time-dependent effects could be assumed to have

increasingly significance. Those factors, such as enhancing in dislocation cross slip and climb, weakening of grain boundaries, cavitation, creep and oxidation, all cause the reduction in fatigue life at elevated temperature. The endurance of the composites again high temperature is stronger than that of the unreinforced aluminum, so the fatigue resistance reduction in the composite was slower. Therefore, the fatigue life of the composites is longer than that of its matrix aluminum under low amplitudes at elevated temperature.

Figure 3. Curves of plastic strain amplitude against number of reversals to failure for the unreinforced aluminum and composite specimens tested at 441K.

The relationship between the cyclic plastic strain amplitude $\Delta\varepsilon_p / 2$ and the number of reversals to failure $2N_f$ fits the Coffin-Manson relationship

$$\frac{1}{2} \Delta\varepsilon_p = \varepsilon'_f (2N_f)^C \tag{1}$$

where ε'_f is fatigue ductility coefficient, C is fatigue ductility exponent. The best straight-line satisfies the plastic strain versus life curves were obtained by linear regression analysis. The parameters associated with the low cycle fatigue properties are illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2. Low cycle fatigue parameters

SiC content (vol%)	SiC size (μm)	Fatigue ductility coefficient	Fatigue ductility exponent	Linear relational coefficient
20	32	10.04	-0.4978	0.9661
0	0	50.56	-0.7212	0.9965

FRACTURE BEHAVIOR

Representative fractographs of the fracture surface features are shown in Fig.4. Fracture surfaces of the composite and the unreinforced matrix specimens revealed nearly similar topographies respectively at low and high plastic strain ranges for a given temperature. Many wide fatigue striations were seen on the fracture surfaces of the unreinforced aluminum shown in Fig.4(a). The fractographs of the composites were significantly different from that of the pure aluminum. On the fracture surfaces of the composite, it was seldom to see striations which were shown in Fig. 4(b). The SiC reinforcement lost efficiency in two method, one was SiCp breaking shown in Fig.4(c), another was interface between SiCp and matrix cohesion as shown in Fig. 4(d).

Figure 4. Topographies of fatigue tests under plastic strain amplitude of (a) 0.24% for Al, (b),(c) 0.16 % for SiCp/Al

CONCLUSIONS

Based on an investigation of the low cycle fatigue behaviors of the SiC particulate reinforced pure aluminum and unreinforced aluminum at 441K, the following conclusions were made.

- (1) The cyclic stress response characteristics of the of composite and its unreinforced aluminum, in the as-extruded condition, were similar to each other in general at elevated temperature. All of them showed continuous cyclic softening behavior except the composite displayed slight cyclic hardening in first loading cycle. In addition, an increase in test frequency led to a higher cyclic stress.
- (2) The SiCp/Al composite and the unreinforced aluminum followed the Coffin-Manson law at elevated temperature. The low cycle fatigue resistance of the composite was lower than that of the unreinforced aluminum under higher cyclic strain ranges, but the fatigue resistance of the composite got stronger at lower cyclic strain amplitudes.

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